

ASSESSMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE QUALITIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The article examines the influence of the guiding communicative qualities of primary school teachers on the development of a democratic, authoritarian and liberal service personality. Psychologist of research work on ensuring the communicative qualities of primary school students.*

Keywords: *pedagogical communication, democratic, authoritarian, liberal, communicative, organization.*

In the process of education, the teacher, by exerting his influence on the student, inculcates personality qualities such as independence and awareness in him, in which self-management is manifested in the form of the "teacher-student" model, where the teacher is the "informer" and the student is the "receiver". showed that the student grows from external reception to independent organization of his activities. The learner learns to control after mastering the methods of a certain system. Therefore, it is important to teach young students self-control, which has a positive effect on the harmonious development of the individual. For this, the elementary school teacher should try to help plan educational activities, improve the qualities of will to think logically, manage interest in learning, organize the learning of working with books, lead team search activities, organize mutual support activities among students, and organize independent activities. he notes that they can develop the ability to consciously manage their personal, moral and mental activities.

In the effectiveness of the "teacher-student" relationship system, we can observe the uniqueness of the teacher's communication style in the process of performing the teacher's main tasks. The tasks of primary school teachers are to help students acquire the necessary level of knowledge, to help them to form skills, to form their perceptions of social reality, to teach them to analyze, to help them compare and generalize; encourage them to become good people; it is to direct them to moral and spiritual maturity, to help them to mature as a person who meets the requirements of society. When we analyzed the evaluations given by the students to the image of the teacher, we witnessed that the student's love for his teachers is unlimited and he is willing to learn the necessary qualities from them. We considered it important to evaluate how teachers themselves are ready for these requirements through their approach, methods and tacts in pedagogical communication, and we started to research it.

It is advisable for the teacher to constantly analyze the technique of organizing communication with the group of students. In certain situations, the pedagogue as a leader directs the students' activities. Communication is a leading factor in this process as well. However, the effectiveness of communication is determined by what communication style is chosen by the pedagogue, who appears as a leader.

Pedagogical activities and other activities of the teacher have their own style. It represents the main aspects of his activity, his individual and psychological characteristics. A teacher's style of activity reflects self-management, influencing others, and the culmination of individual

experiences. For this reason, while observing the relationship of teachers with students, we researched their authoritarian, democratic, carefree pedagogical methods.

In the research, we also took into account the study of the pedagogical style of the teacher in his relationship with students in harmony with his personal qualities. For this, we found it necessary to study by comparing the teacher's pedagogical methods. In this L.P. We used Kalininsky's methodology "Assessment of organizational and communicative qualities of a person" (see the appendix). In this, we mainly achieved an assessment of the organizational and communicative qualities of elementary school teachers.

When comparing the organizational and communicative qualities of authoritarian and liberal style teachers, almost no reliability differences were observed. Therefore, we can talk about some cases of their results. In general, according to the test results, the results of pedagogues working in a democratic style were much higher than those of authoritarian teachers. The communicative capabilities of democratic style teachers are much higher. This was observed in their qualities related to diligence, self-confidence, demandingness and psychological tact (Table 1).

Table 1

Comparative indicators of the results of teachers with authoritarian and democratic pedagogical style

№	Adjectives	Authoritarian	Democratic	P
1	Orientation	4,9 ± 0,46	7,1 ± 1,12	0,75
2	Psychological preparation for organizational work	7,3 ± 0,71	9,8 ± 0,87	0,82
3	Striving for dominance	8,90 ± 0,52	4,4 ± 0,82	0,7
4	Self confidence	4,7 ± 0,61	5,5 ± 0,68	0,32
5	Demanding	3,5 ± 0,57	4,9 ± 0,83	0,69
6	Caesarism	3,3 ± 0,78	4,6 ± 0,8	-
7	Fun	5,3 ± 1,32	6,8 ± 1,49	0,43
8	Dependency	5 ± 1,21	5,7 ± 1,35	0
9	Psychological tact	7,1. ± 0,66	8,92 ± 1,25	0,88
10	A sense of sympathy	5,7 ± 1,34	7,7 ± 1,11	0,91

The results of the orientation scale (0.75) of teachers working in a democratic style were significantly different than those of authoritarian teachers. Differences in their average values are reflected in the intellect, worldview of teachers who work in a democratic style, striving to achieve the common goals of the team. Their needs are aligned with the overall team goals. The results related to this scale are much lower in teachers who work in an authoritarian style. There was also some difference between the results on the performance scale (0.82). We think that this quality is important for teachers. Although this quality is somewhat higher in teachers with a democratic working style, it has its own scope in authoritarian teachers as well. The positive nature of the results indicates the desire to develop the qualities of work and organization.

The fact that teachers with a democratic style of activity have higher results on the scale of dominance can be said to be a surprising fact. Their results were observed to differ from those of authoritarian teachers (0.7). According to the average value, a difference was observed in the

second group compared to the first group. As the sample of primary school teachers was studied as the reason for these results, it is sufficient for this stage of education to have some basic level of democratic working style. For this reason, the results of this scale were not very high. This can be explained by the low desire for leadership and power. There was a difference in the demand scales of both categories of teachers (0.69). Although this scale showed a higher than average result in democratic style teachers, their results are not in the zone of potential development. Accordingly, it can be said that teachers of democratic style are demanding people and are determined to achieve their goals.

According to the scale of psychological tact, differences were observed in the results of authoritarian and democratic style teachers (0.88). The indicators of teachers on this scale are quite high. Of course, it is natural for teachers with a democratic style to have a high psychological tact. They have clarity. In the relationship with students, there is a norm and etiquette of communication. They are able to influence those around them and react according to their individual characteristics. He can find the necessary tone of communication with children. He is courteous and polite, and responds immediately to natural appeals. It would be desirable if all primary school teachers had this quality. This is an important quality for every elementary school teacher. Unfortunately, it is difficult to find such quality owners everywhere. But we believe that it is important to focus on the formation of psychological tact qualities in the process of professional and personal development of teachers. Therefore, in our psychocorrective program, their cooperation in improving the relationship between teachers and students is taken into account. In fact, we believe that the issue of pedagogical activity styles of teachers will be the subject of a new research problem.

Conclusion. Based on the results of our research, we can draw some conclusions:

- There are differences between the owners of authoritarian and democratic style of communication, and they are embodied in: a) teachers with democratic style have much higher communicative capabilities, self-confidence, diligence, demandingness and psychological tact. With this, the owners of this style can be said to be effective communicators.

In the case of an authoritarian pedagogy, avoidance of communicative situations was observed. They are characterized by independence, self-restraint, and lack of communication skills.

- Personality traits that characterize the communication style of democratic and authoritarian teachers are also different. For democrats, it is reflected in emotional stability, trustworthiness, sensitivity, responsibility, and attention to self-control, while in authoritarians, it is reflected in reactive balance, boldness, tension of character, overconfidence, and suspicion.

- The differences in communication between authoritarian and democratic teachers are related to their emotional sphere. Signs of discomfort can be observed in the democratic style. These teachers feel empowered and their needs are met. The professional activity of teachers requires the ability to work and to achieve the expected result. The emotional sphere of teachers with demandingness, diligence, work orientation, democratic work style towards themselves and others.

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